

Parthenin from *Parthenium hysterophorus*, its conversion to anhydroparthenin by conventional and microwave methods and their antimicrobial activity

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Manuscript received 16 November 2009, revised 18 March 2010, accepted 7 April 2010

Abstract : Parthenin, sesquiterpenelactone has been isolated from the aerial parts of *Parthenium hysterophorus* along with stigmasterol, β -sitosterol, isoparthenin, coronopilin and 11,13-dihydroparthenin. The compound has been converted into anhydroparthenin by conventional and microwave methods. The compounds were characterized by their spectral (IR mass, ^1H , ^{13}C NMR) data and evaluated for their antibacterial activities against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and antifungal activity against *Aspergillus niger*, *Candida albicans*, *Fusarium oxysporum*.

Keywords : *Parthenium hysterophorus*, Asteraceae, sesquiterpenelactones, γ -butyrolactone, microwave irradiation.

Introduction

Parthenium hysterophorus belongs to the family Asteraceae and is commonly called as congress grass, congress weed, carrot weed and wild feverfew. The "Scourge of India" is an exotic weed that was accidentally introduced in India in 1956 through imported food grains and is now considered as one of the most feared noxious weed¹. Parthenin is a sesquiterpenoid having a pseudoguaianolide structure. It is interesting for its structural pattern² as well as for its bioactivity including anti-malarial³, anti-amoebic⁴ and allelopathic^{5,6} properties.

Microwave irradiation, although occasionally known by such acronyms as 'MEC' (Microwave-Enhanced Chemistry) or MORE synthesis (Microwave-organic Reaction Enhancement), is becoming an increasingly popular method of heating which replaces the classical one as it proves to be a clean, cheap and convenient method^{7,8}. This method of heating has been extended to almost all areas of organic chemistry⁹. We have isolated various constituents of *Parthenium hysterophorus* including stigmasterol, isoparthenin, coronopilin, β -sitosterol, 11,13-dihydroparthenin, parthenin and prepared anhydroparthenin from parthenin by conventional and microwave methods. The two compounds at different concentrations were screened for antibacterial and antifungal activity against the bacteria *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and fungi *Aspergillus niger*, *Candida albicans*, *Fusarium oxysporum* respectively.

Results and discussion

The aerial parts were exhaustively extracted with petroleum ether to remove fats. The plant material is then treated with dichloromethane, diethylether, methanol (1 : 1 : 1) at room temperature for 24 h. The resulting extract was concentrated in vacuum, dissolved in methanol and left overnight. Elution of column with benzene : ethyl acetate mixture afforded parthenin (1).

The IR spectrum of 1 exhibited absorption peak in the region 3450 cm^{-1} due to hydroxyl group, and other peaks are at 1755 , 1655 , 1718 and 1592 cm^{-1} . In ^1H NMR, a pair of doublets appears at 7.63 and 6.15 ppm due to olefinic H-2 and H-3 protons respectively. A pair of doublets appears at 6.25 and 5.61 ppm due to exomethylene protons. A doublet at 5.02 ppm was due to proton under oxygen function (H-6) and a multiplet at 3.53 ppm correspondingly to H-7 proton. Singlet at 1.27 ppm and a doublet at 1.11 ppm correspond to methyl at C-5, C-10 respectively. The mass spectrum shows a prominent molecular ion peak at m/z 262 establishing $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{18}\text{O}_4$ as its molecular formula. The ^{13}C NMR spectrum showed signals related to 15 C atoms in the compound.

We have converted this parthenin into anhydroparthenin by both conventional and microwave methods (Scheme 1). A comparative study in terms of reaction time and yield of compound shows that in comparison to conventional method yield was better in microwave method, moreover in microwave method the reaction is

Scheme 1

complete within 5–6 min as compared to conventional method, which requires 3–4 h.

Parthenin was reacted with acetic anhydride in the presence of sodium hydrogen sulfate supported on silica gel ($\text{NaHSO}_4 \cdot \text{SiO}_2$)¹⁰ as a catalyst at room temperature. The conversion solely led to the formation of the naturally occurring sesquiterpenoid, anhydroparthenin (2)¹¹.

The IR spectrum of 2 doesn't show absorption peak in the region 3450 cm^{-1} due to hydroxyl group, but shows peaks at 1755 , 1655 , 1710 , 1580 , 1560 cm^{-1} . In ^1H NMR, a pair of doublets appears at 6.25 and 5.61 ppm due to exomethylene protons. A pair of doublets appears at 7.55 and 6.10 ppm due to olefinic H-2 and H-3 protons respectively. A doublet 5.02 ppm was due to proton under oxygen function (H-6) and a multiplet at 3.53 ppm correspondingly to H-7 proton. Singlet at 1.27 ppm and 1.2 ppm corresponds to methyl at C-5, C-10 respectively. The mass spectrum shows a prominent molecular ion peak at m/z 244 establishing $\text{C}_{15}\text{H}_{16}\text{O}_3$ as its molecular formula.

Antibacterial and antifungal activity :

Parthenin and anhydroparthenin at 4 concentrations viz. 200, 400, 600, 800 ppm were also screened for antibacterial and antifungal activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli*, *Pseudomonas aeruginosa* and fungi *Aspergillus niger*, *Candida albicans*, *Fusarium oxysporum* respectively at different concentration by disk diffusion method¹². Gentamycin and mycostatin are used

as reference compounds for evaluating antibacterial and antifungal activities respectively. It was observed that activity of parthenin was better than anhydroparthenin. The former shows good activity against *Staphylococcus aureus*, *Escherichia coli* and fungi *Candida albicans*, *Fusarium oxysporum* respectively. Anhydroparthenin shows comparable activity against *Escherichia coli* and fungi *Candida albicans* and a moderate activity against other tested organisms. The results obtained are presented in Tables 1 and 2.

Table 1. Antibacterial activity of parthenin and anhydroparthenin

		Mean value of area of inhibition in mm IZ (AI)		
Bacteria →		<i>Staphylococcus aureus</i>	<i>Escherichia coli</i>	<i>Pseudomonas aeruginosa</i>
Gentamycin → (Control)		10	6.9	12
Test samples	Conc. (ppm)			
1	200	8.1 (0.81)	8.2 (1.18)	5.1 (0.42)
1	400	8.4 (0.84)	8.5 (1.23)	5.5 (0.45)
1	600	9.1 (0.91)	9.0 (1.30)	5.2 (0.43)
1	800	9.5 (0.95)	9.4 (1.36)	5.3 (0.44)
2	200	5.0 (0.50)	7.0 (1.01)	5.2 (0.43)

Note

Table-1 (contd.)

2	400	5.2 (0.52)	7.8 (1.13)	5.5 (0.45)
2	600	5.5 (0.55)	8.5 (1.23)	5.7 (0.47)
2	800	6.0 (0.60)	8.8 (1.27)	6.0 (0.50)

IZ = Inhibition area excluding diameter of disk.

AI = Activity index = Inhibition area of sample/Inhibition area of standard.

Table 2. Antifungal activity of parthenin and anhydroparthenin

		Mean value of area of inhibition in mm IZ (percent mycelial zone inhibition)		
Fungi →		<i>Candida albicans</i>	<i>Aspergillus niger</i>	<i>Fusarium oxysporum</i>
Mycostatin → (Control)		12	9	10.1
Test samples	Conc. (ppm)			
1	200	9.1 (0.24)	5.9 (0.34)	7.8 (0.22)
1	400	9.2 (0.23)	6.1 (0.32)	8.0 (0.20)
1	600	9.4 (0.21)	6.3 (0.30)	8.5 (0.15)
1	800	9.6 (0.2)	6.6 (0.26)	8.5 (0.15)
2	200	8.4 (0.30)	5.1 (0.43)	4.2 (0.58)
2	400	8.5 (0.29)	5.2 (0.42)	4.5 (0.55)
2	600	8.8 (0.26)	5.4 (0.40)	5.0 (0.50)
2	800	9.1 (0.24)	5.7 (0.36)	5.5 (0.45)

IZ = Inhibition area excluding diameter of disk.

$$\text{Percent mycelial zone inhibition} = \frac{dc - dt}{dc}$$

Here *dc* and *dt* are diameters of mycelial colony of control and treated sets.

Experimental

General : Melting points were determined in open glass capillary tube and are uncorrected. Column chromatography : silica gel. Preparative TLC : Merck silica gel. 60F₂₅₄ precoated glass plates. IR spectra (cm⁻¹) were recorded on Shimadzu FTIR-8400 spectrophotometer in

KBr disc and noteworthy absorptions levels (cm⁻¹) are listed. ¹H and ¹³C NMR spectra were recorded on Jeol AL 300 MHz and Bruker Avance DRX 500 FT spectrometers using TMS as internal standard (chemical shift, δ in ppm and *J* in Hz). Mass spectra were determined by Jeol SX-102 (FAB) spectrometer.

Plant material : The aerial part of *Parthenium hysterophorus* was collected from Kala khet, Kota and identification was done with help of Department of Botany, Govt. College, Kota.

Extraction and isolation : The aerial parts (3 kg) were exhaustively extracted with pet. ether. The plant material is then treated with dichloromethane, diethyl ether, methanol (1 : 1 : 1) at room temperature for 24 h. The resulting extract (30 g) was concentrated in vacuum, dissolved in methanol and left overnight. The methanol soluble part was subjected to column chromatography over silica gel. Five fractions were obtained from the column. Fraction 1 (pet ether : benzene, 3 : 2) afforded stigmasterol as colourless shining needles 120 mg, m.p. 165 °C. Fraction 2 (pet ether : benzene, 2 : 3) afforded β-sitosterol as colourless needles 140 mg, m.p. 136 °C. Fraction 3 (benzene : EtOAc, 4 : 1) reveals the presence of two compounds upon TLC. After repeated preparative TLC two compounds were isolated, parthenin as colourless prismatic crystals 220 mg, m.p. 165 °C and isoparthenin as colourless gum, 30 mg. Fraction 4 (benzene : EtOAc, 3 : 2) afforded 11,13-dihydroparthenin as colourless crystals 30 mg, m.p. 185 °C. Fraction 5 (benzene : EtOAc, 1 : 4) afforded coronopilin as colourless needles 70 mg, m.p. 178 °C.

Preparation of anhydroparthenin from parthenin by conventional method : To a stirred solution of parthenin (100 mg), Ac₂O (1 ml) was added in CH₂Cl₂ (10 ml). After 5 min NaHSO₄·SiO₂ (300 mg) was added and stirring was continued for 2.5 h at room temperature. The mixture was filtered and the filtrate was concentrated and subjected to column chromatography over silica gel using hexane-EtOAc (9 : 1) as an eluent to yield anhydroparthenin (2) (78%).

Preparation of anhydroparthenin from parthenin by microwave method :

In the microwave experiment, we selected low, middle

and high power of microwave irradiation respectively (the commercial LG domestic microwave oven only have three choices).

Mixture of parthenin, Ac_2O and silica gel in CH_2Cl_2 was irradiated at 300 W (25% MW power) under microwave irradiation for 4 to 6 min with a short interval of 5 to 30 s to avoid excess evaporation of solvent. After completion of reaction checked by TLC, the reaction mixture was cooled, filtered and the filtrate was concentrated and subjected to column chromatography over silica gel using hexane-EtOAc (9 : 1) as a eluent to yield anhydroparthenin (2) (82%).

Acknowledgement

The authors are thankful to Dr. Ashok Sharma, Microbiologist, RDDC, Kota for evaluation of biological activity. We are also thankful to UGC, New Delhi for financial assistance.

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